

Hydroxamic Acid as Donors. Chromium (III) Complexes with Hydroxamic Acids

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Hydroxamic acid complexes, $[\text{Cr}(\text{RH})_3]^0$ have been prepared and their structures assigned on the basis of molar conductance, magnetic and spectral measurements. Magnetic moments show three unpaired electrons per chromium for each complex. The complexes have two d-d transitions in the visible region.

Hydroxamic acids with RCONHOH grouping (R = aryl or alkyl radical) have been used widely as spectrophotometric reagent¹ and extracting reagent². Successful attempt has been made by many workers to isolate stable crystalline salts with hydroxamic acids³⁻¹¹. The aromatic hydroxamic acids studied include, Benzo-(BH₂); Salicyl-(SH₂); *p*-chloro Benzo-(*p*-chloro BH₂); *p*-Anisyl-(*p*-AH₂); *p*-nitro Benzo-(*p*-nitro BH₂); Nicotino(NiCH₂); Phenyl acet-(Phenylacet H₂) and Cyclohexane hydroxamic acid (CH₂). In general, it was observed that aqueous solution of chrome alum (one mole) reacts with any one of these hydroxamic acids (four moles) to provide green complexes. The insoluble product was identified to be tris-(hydroxamato)-chromium (III).

The complexes are not fairly soluble in methanol. The molar conductance values have been reported (Table III), for those which are soluble. The data give, as expected, non-electrolyte values.

The magnetic moments, reported in Table III, are in good agreement with spin only value for three unpaired electrons, characteristic for Cr(III) and indicates d²Sp³ bonding in the complexes.

Most of the complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents, so reflectance spectra for the complexes have been taken. The spectra of the complexes are typical of octahedral

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TABLE I
Reflectance spectra of the complexes

Complex	λ_{max} (m μ)	Wave number (cm $^{-1}$)	Assignment
[Cr(<i>p</i> -nitro BH) ₃]	430	23,260	${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$
	620	16,130	${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$
[Cr(NiCH) ₃]	430—450	22,220—23,260	${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$
	600—620	16,130—16,670	${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$
[Cr(Phenyl acet.H) ₃]	420—430	23,260—23,810	${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$
	610	16,400	${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$
[Cr(CH) ₃]	430—440	22,730—22,260	${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$
	610	16,400	${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$

Cr(III) complexes. The spectral data for a few of the complexes are given in Table I and illustrated in Fig. 1. The bands around 16,000 cm $^{-1}$ have been assigned to transitions derived from ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ and the bands around 22,500 cm $^{-1}$ have been assigned to transitions derived from ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ in the octahedral field. The first ligand field band, ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ for Cr $^{3+}$ (d^3) ion corresponds to 10Dq values. The Dq values for a given metal ion

usually correlate with the coordinating ability. The Dq values obtained for these ligands are compared with that of water in the octahedral complexes for Cr(III). The spectrochemical series of ligands as obtained from Cr(III) complexes are :

IR spectra for a few complexes have been taken. The lowering of C = O stretch and increase of C-N stretch of the ligands in the complexes indicate that coordination of hydroxamic acid is through carbonyl oxygen. The carbonyl band at 1660 cm $^{-1}$ in benzohydroxamic acid is shifted to 1587 cm $^{-1}$ and CN bond frequency at 1320 cm $^{-1}$ in the free reagent goes over to 1342 cm $^{-1}$ in the tris (benzohydroxamato)-chromium (III) complex (Table II). This is true for other complexes of chromium.

TABLE II

Infrared spectra (cm⁻¹)

BH ₂	III [Cr(BH) ₃]	BH ₂	III [Cr(BH) ₃]	
710		1500	1563	
805	803	1580	1587	br
910	909	1660		
1030	1020	2810	2857	
1052	1042	3070		br
		3300	3333	
1170				
1320	1342			
1450	1471			

br = broad.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Hydroxamic acids are prepared by following standard procedures^{12,13}. Cyclohexane hydroxamic acid (CH₂) is prepared as follows.

Anhydrous hydroxylamine hydrochloride (7.7 g.) was dissolved in anhydrous methanol (40 ml.) by refluxing on a steam bath. Potassium hydroxide (9.5 g.) was similarly dissolved in anhydrous methanol (25 ml). The two solutions were cooled and mixed and precipitated KCl filtered off. Ethyl ester of cyclohexane acid (8 g.) was then added to it, mixed well and left for 40 hrs. at room temperature. It was then concentrated by evaporation under a fan, cooled in ice and cyclohexane hydroxamic acid was precipitated by the addition of dilute HCl. It was then filtered and recrystallised twice from hot water. The final product is a white crystalline solid having m.p. 125–126°. Found : N, 9.65%. Required for C₇H₁₂NO₂ : N, 9.8%.

Tis-(Benzohydroxamate)-Cr(III) (Green) : An aqueous solution of chrome alum (one mole) and aqueous solution of benzohydroxamic acid (four moles) were mixed and heated in water bath for 15 min when a green ppt. appeared. This was allowed to stand for a few minutes, filtered, washed several times with distilled water and dried over CaCl₂.

Other complexes were prepared by following the same procedure. The analytical data are given in Table III.

Analyses : The chromium in the complex was estimated iodometrically and nitrogen by combustion technique.

The conductance of complexes in methanol was determined by Philips conductivity bridge and dip-type cell. The cell constant was 0.6794 cm⁻¹.

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TABLE III

Analytical data, molar conductance values and magnetic moments of the complexes

Complex	Analytical data		Molar conductance (ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹)	Magnetic moment (μ eff.) (B.M.)
	%Cr	%N		
[Cr(BH) ₃]	F : 11.30	9.0	14.1	3.75
	R : 11.31	9.13		
[Cr(SH) ₃]	F : 10.18	8.2	8.3	3.80
	R : 10.23	8.27		
[Cr(NiCH) ₃]	F : 11.50	18.6	—	3.80
	R : 11.42	18.5		
[Cr(<i>o</i> -nitro BH) ₃]	F : 8.7	14.2	—	3.70
	R : 8.74	14.12		
[Cr(<i>p</i> -chloro BH) ₃]	F : 9.25	7.5	—	3.80
	R : 9.23	7.45		
[Cr(Phenylacet.H) ₃]	F : 10.3	8.4	—	3.80
	R : 10.36	8.37		
[Cr(CH) ₃]	F : 11.65	8.70	—	3.75
	R : 11.71	8.80		
[Cr(<i>p</i> -AH) ₃]	F : 9.5	7.6	—	3.80
	R : 9.45	7.63		

The IR spectra were recorded by the KBr disc method using Parkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer.

The reflectance spectra were recorded on Hilger-Uvispeck Spectrophotometer following Lee, Griswold and Kleinberg¹⁴.

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